

OPTIMAL COOLING FOR MINIMUM RESIDUAL STRESSES

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ABSTRACT

During the cooling of a fiber-reinforced viscoelastic part, internal stresses develop due to not only the temperature gradient in the part but also the differential thermal contraction between the fibers and matrix. Crack or warping may occur if the stresses are too high. In order to reduce the residual stresses, the cooling process must be very slow to have small temperature gradient and maximum stress relaxation. The goal of this study is to find an optimal thermal history within a specified time period for minimum residual stresses in composites parts. The development of the internal stresses caused by temperature gradient and differential thermal contraction during the cooling is first presented. The stresses are then minimized through optimization of the thermal history of the process. The surface temperature of the part is chosen as the control variable while the thermal field in the part represents the state variables. Euler-Lagrange equations are solved with first gradient algorithm to iterate the optimal solution. Physical insights are provided for the optimal cooling path predicted theoretically.

INTRODUCTION

The analysis of thermal stresses in viscoelastic materials must take into consideration the temperature dependent properties. Some analyses¹ have idealized these properties by assuming inviscid behavior above and elastic behavior below the critical temperature referred to as the glass transition temperature of an amorphous polymer. Such models neglect the important stress relaxation property of viscoelastic materials. Later, a material model termed "thermorheologically simple" was also proposed.^{2,3} This model exhibits a pure shift in relaxation function plotted against the logarithm of time when there is a temperature change. The relaxation functions measured at two temperatures, T_1 and T_2 , are related simply by a change in the time scale with a factor $\phi(T_2)/\phi(T_1)$, which reduces the time scale as the temperature increases. In other words, the stresses relax faster at higher temperature. Therefore, it is convenient to define a reduced time ψ which includes the varying scale factor $\phi(T)$ so that the viscoelastic stress-strain relation under a continuously varying temperature has the same form as the isothermal relation.

Muki and Sternberg⁴ employed this material model to investigate the thermal stresses of a bounded plate when the plate is cooled symmetrically from both surfaces. The plate's lateral dimensions are much larger than the thickness and the lateral displacement is completely constrained. The final thermal stresses after cooling can be expressed as

$$\sigma_{xx} = -3\alpha_0 \int_0^{t_i} R(\xi(z, t)) \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \theta(z, t) dt, \quad (1)$$

where

$$R(\xi) = L^{-1} \left(\frac{G_1(s)G_2(s)}{2G_1(s) + G_2(s)} \right), \quad G_1 = \frac{E}{(1+\nu)}, \quad G_2 = \frac{E}{(1-2\nu)},$$

$$\xi(z, t) = \int_1^{t_i} \phi(\theta(z, \lambda)) d\lambda, \quad \theta = T - T_0.$$

ϕ is the time-temperature shift factor and α_0 is the coefficient of thermal expansion. Weitsman et al.^{5,6} and Gurtin et al.⁷ considered the cooling of a fiber-reinforced composite laminate without temperature gradient in the laminate. The residual thermal stress at the resin-fiber interface due to differential coefficients of thermal expansion is given by

$$\sigma = -C \int_0^{t_i} G(\xi(z, t)) \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \theta(z, t) dt, \quad (2)$$

where

$$C = 2 \left(\frac{1+\nu}{1-\nu} \right) (\alpha_m - \alpha_r).$$

Since equations (1) and (2) have similar integral forms, equation (1) will be used in this paper to demonstrate the method of optimizing the cooling history of a fiber-reinforced composite with temperature gradient in the part.

The analyses of thermal stresses in viscoelastic materials with temperature gradient require the consideration of temperature dependent properties and the thermal contraction. Therefore, the transient thermal field in the plate during the cooling should first be determined. For a step change of surface temperature in a plate from T_0 to T_w , the transient temperature distributions can be given as⁸

$$\frac{T - T_w}{T_0 - T_w} = \frac{4}{\pi} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n} \exp \left(- \left(\frac{n\pi}{2L} \right)^2 \alpha t \right) \sin \left(\frac{n\pi z}{2L} \right), \quad n = 1, 3, 5, \dots \quad (3)$$

where T_0 is the initial temperature, T_w is the surface temperature, α is the thermal diffusivity and $2L$ is the thickness of the plate. For simplicity, the function on the right hand side is represented by $f(z, t)$.

$$\frac{T - T_w}{T_0 - T_w} = f(z, t). \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) can then be rearranged to be

$$\frac{\theta}{\theta_w} = \frac{T - T_0}{T_w - T_0} = 1 - f(z, t). \quad (5)$$

If θ_w varies over time, superposition requires that

$$\theta(z, t) = \int_0^t \theta_w(\lambda) \frac{\partial}{\partial \lambda} f(z, t - \lambda) d\lambda . \quad (6)$$

Taking the derivative of equation (6) with respect to time gives

$$\dot{\theta}(z, t) = \int_0^t \theta_w(\lambda) \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t \partial \lambda} f(z, t - \lambda) d\lambda - \dot{f}(z, 0) \theta_w(t) . \quad (7)$$

The results of equation (7) are used in equations (1) and (2) to determine the transient and final thermal stress distributions. The time-temperature shift factor $\phi(T)$ assumes the W.L.F. form⁹. The function $R(\xi)$ for polymethyl methacrylate at 80°C was also measured and estimated by Muki et al.⁴. They used the asymptotic method to find the inverse Laplace transform for $R(\xi)$.

OPTIMAL COOLING

An optimal thermal history, which cools the plate from θ_0 to θ_1 within a specified period between $t=0$ to $t=t_f$ and results in minimum thermal stresses at $t=t_f$, is to be found in this section. It is assumed that the temperature $\theta_w(t)$ on the surfaces of the plate can be varied as a function of time. The optimal thermal history of $\theta_w(t)$ for minimum thermal stresses is to be determined.

Equation (1) can be used to calculate the stress at any point across the thickness of the plate. Therefore, the final stresses at any location, z_0 , in the plate can be chosen to be minimized.

$$\sigma(z_0, t_f) = -3\alpha_0 \int_0^{t_f} R(\xi(z_0, t)) \dot{\theta}(z_0, t) dt . \quad (8)$$

In addition, a performance measure I is defined as the square of the stress since the magnitude of stress is to be minimized.

$$I = \left\{ -3\alpha_0 \int_0^{t_f} R(\xi(z_0, t)) \dot{\theta}(z_0, t) dt \right\}^2 . \quad (9)$$

We can also define I as the summation of stress square at locations across the thickness if the entire stress field is to be minimized.

Half thickness of the plate is divided into 20 nodes and the temperatures of the nodes are the state variables. $\dot{\theta}(z, t)$, $f(z, t - \lambda)$ and $\dot{f}(z, 0)$ in equation (7), therefore, are in vector forms. Equation (7) will be used as the system equation to determine the transient thermal field. This optimal control problem is to find an admissible control $\theta_w(t)$ that causes the system to follow an admissible trajectory $\theta(z, t)$ which is prescribed at $t=0$ and $t=t_f$, and minimizes the performance measure I expressed in equation (9). The terminal constraints of this optimal control problem can be specified as

$$\theta(z, 0) = 0, \quad \theta(z, t_f) = \theta_f . \quad (10)$$

A terminal function in vector form, therefore, can be defined as

$$N(\theta(z, t_r)) = \theta(z, t_r) - \theta_r = 0 \quad (11)$$

The approach of Bryson and Denham¹⁰, which separated the problems of minimizing I with the constraint equation (7), and satisfying both equation (7) and $N=0$ simultaneously, was employed here. Euler-Lagrange equations were solved with first gradient numerical iteration to obtain the optimal cooling profile.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Since the surface of the plate cools the fastest across the thickness, which implies the least stress relaxation, the final stress on the surface is expected to be the largest across the thickness of the plate. The surface stress was then chosen to be minimized first. Figure 1 shows the surface temperature histories of quenching, linear and optimal coolings. The corresponding final thermal stress distributions across half of the plate are given in Figure 2. Quenching gives the largest surface stress while the optimal cooling leads to smallest surface stress although the reduction is small. The optimal thermal history of the surface presents an initial temperature drop followed by a slow cooling for most of the cooling period. Since the temperature across the thickness of the plate should reach the final temperature at the end of the cooling, the surface temperature should drop to the final temperature well before the end of the cooling. Although the final temperature drop would produce surface stress that cannot relax, the optimal cooling still results in minimum surface stress.

Weitsman et al.^{5,6} and Gurtin et al.⁷ also investigated the optimal cooling of a fiber-reinforced composite with uniform temperature in the part. The resulting optimal cooling history also shows two discontinuities at the beginning and the end of the cooling path, which correspond to the initial and final drops of temperature in Figure 1. However, with the consideration of temperature gradient in the present study, the surface temperature must drop to the final temperature before the end of cooling so that the temperature inside the plate will reach the final temperature at the end of the cooling. If only the surface temperature and surface stress are considered for optimal cooling, the result would be the same as that presented by Weitsman et al.^{5,6} and Gurtin et al.⁷

Physical insight of the optimal cooling path is explained in the following. Since the initial and final temperatures are fixed, the total thermal strain resulting from the cooling of a bounded plate is constant. A temperature drop at the beginning would generate strain and therefore stress in the very early stage which would allow more time for stress relaxation due to the fixed period of cooling. A temperature drop in the very beginning is, therefore, desired.

The degree of the temperature drop in the beginning also affects the stress relaxation because the relaxation time constant increases with decreasing temperature. Although a larger temperature drop in the beginning will produce higher stress and leave a long period for stress relaxation, only a small amount of stress will relax because of the low temperature. On the other hand, the stress resulting from a smaller initial temperature drop would relax quickly due to the high temperature. However, the stresses resulting from the larger final temperature drop would not have time to relax. The trade-off between the thermal strain and the temperature has led to the optimal cooling history for maximum stress relaxation.

The optimal cooling profile for minimizing the entire stress field across the thickness, rather than the stress at a given point, is presented in Figure 3. In other words, the summation of the stress at every node across the thickness is defined as the performance measure I. The initial drop of the surface temperature is larger in this case than that in Figure 1 in order for the average temperature across the thickness to follow the same path as in Figure 1 because the entire stress field is minimized. The resulting stress distributions are given in Figure 4. Obviously, the entire stress field is smaller than that in Figure 2 since it is the target of minimization. However, the surface stress is larger than that in Figure 2 because the surface stress rather than the entire stress field is minimized in Figure 2. The performance measure I in Figure 2 is the surface stress while that in Figure 4 is the summation of stress across the thickness.

CONCLUSIONS

The goal of this research is to find an optimal thermal history within a specified time period for minimizing residual thermal stresses in viscoelastic materials. The surface temperature of a plate was chosen as the control variable and temperature gradient inside the plate was considered. Euler-Lagrange equations were solved with first gradient algorithm to iterate the solutions. The optimal cooling profiles for minimizing the surface stress as well as the entire stress field were studied. The optimal cooling profile presents an initial temperature drop followed by a slow cooling for most of the cooling period. The surface temperature stays on this path until the time that it has to drop to the final temperature so that the temperature inside the plate can reach the final temperature at the end of the cooling. Although the final temperature drop produces stress that cannot relax, the final stress is still a minimum. Physical interpretation of the optimal cooling profile has also been given. The analytical expression of residual thermal stress between the fiber and the matrix in fiber-reinforced composite is similar to that of a bounded plate if the fibers are assumed rigid. Therefore, the optimal cooling profile of the composite for minimum residual stresses at the interface can also be obtained through the solution algorithm of the bounded plate.

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Figure 1: Temperature Profiles of Quenching, Linear and Optimal Coolings for Minimum Surface Stress.

Figure 2: Final Thermal Stresses from Quenching, Linear and Optimal Cooling for Minimum Surface Stress.

Figure 3: Temperature Profiles of Quenching, Linear and Optimal Coolings for Minimum Entire Stress Field.

Figure 4: Final Thermal Stresses from Quenching, Linear and Optimal Coolings for Minimum Entire Stress Field.